

Research Software Alliance

2024 COMMUNITY REPORT

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INTRODUCTION

In 2024, the Research Software Alliance (ReSA) continued to make significant contributions to the international research software community. ReSA engages with multiple stakeholder interests and advances the recognition and value of research software, including those who develop and maintain it. By working closely with decision-makers and key influencers, we strive to advance the research software ecosystem and foster collaboration across diverse sectors.

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ReSA brings together a wide range of stakeholders, from national and regional organisations to disciplinary and thematic initiatives, to achieve shared objectives. Our community includes numerous research software organisations and networks that span the globe, working towards the creation of a united and resilient ecosystem.

We are excited to share key highlights from 2024 and look forward to what we aim to accomplish in 2025 and beyond. ReSA plays a crucial role in the scholarly landscape to enhance sustainability and resilience by cultivating a global research software community that can adapt to the evolving needs of research stakeholders worldwide.

IMPACT

RESEARCH SOFTWARE FUNDERS FORUM

ReSA has led the development of the Research Software Funders Forum, which has engaged more than **60 funding organisations** and 90 individuals from across the globe since its inception in 2022. The Funders Forum has been working to address common challenges to achieve the significant cultural change needed across the research sector and better coordinate investment globally. The Funders Forum serves a broad range of newcomers and experienced research software funders. The diversity of experience and perspectives of both newcomers and returning participants has created a global community that is changing funders' understanding of research software and their investments in it.

In 2024, a key outcome of the Funders Forum's work was the inclusion of a research software side event at the Global Research Council (GRC) annual meeting in Interlaken, Switzerland. The proposal was led by the Dutch Research Council (NWO), German Research Foundation (DFG), and the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP). This side event focused on gaps related to research software in the current global funding and policy environment, and suggested concrete actions that research funding organisations can take to address them.

Image by Daniel S. Katz

ADORE.SOFTWARE

The [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#) (ADORE.software) is a first step to formalise, on a global level, the basic principles and recommendations related to funding the sustainability of research software, including the people needed to achieve this goal. In 2024, ADORE.software broadened the criteria of who can be a signatory to include individuals as well as organisations (see [version 1.1](#)). You can show your support by joining the list of individuals and organisations to [become a signatory](#), or find out more in the [FAQ](#). ReSA has also been actively updating ADORE.software's complementary [toolkit](#) to include new information that supports the Declaration.

FUNDERS WORKSHOP

In September, more than 50 funders and experts in research software gathered in Uppsala, Sweden, and online, for the third annual [International Research Software Funders Workshop](#). [SciLifeLab](#), [SciLifeLab Data Centre](#), and ReSA co-hosted this workshop, which focused on operationalising ADORE.software. The workshop was facilitated by [Eric Jensen](#), a monitoring and evaluation expert. Participants discussed developing funders' monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess what is working and why in funders' support for research software impact.

Prior to the funders workshop, [EVERSE](#) (European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence), SciLifeLab Data Centre, and ReSA convened a hybrid satellite event. During this full-day [workshop](#),

the EVERSE project showcased its work, received feedback from key stakeholders, and promoted networking and collaboration among attendees. Presentations from the two events are available on [Zenodo](#).

Image by SciLifeLab

Image by SciLifeLab

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Image by Sean Goggins

Research Software Infrastructure (RSI) Forum

Launched by ReSA in late 2024, the Research Software Infrastructure (RSI) Forum is a collaboration of infrastructure organisations. It aims to understand common challenges faced by the infrastructures that support research software, particularly as research software plays an increasing role in research.

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Infrastructure organisations play a key role in the development, maintenance, sharing, and connectivity of research software through services like software registries, repositories, journals, sustainability efforts, and preservation initiatives. The RSI Forum’s mission is twofold: (1) to enable collaborations among infrastructure providers and (2) to increase the sharing of practices for research software infrastructures, encouraging reflection and advancement.

Since its inaugural meeting in October, RSI Forum members have focused on use cases, exploring how different activities related to research software use elements of the research software ecosystem, while also discussing cross-cutting topics such as metadata and identifiers.

Membership is open to infrastructure organisations that serve research software—from development and maintenance to sharing and connectivity.

International research software event scoping

In 2024, with support from the [Alfred P. Sloan Foundation](#), ReSA engaged stakeholders to explore and recommend pathways for the first international research software conference. This effort began by consulting existing events for insights, resulting in [Towards an International Research Software Conference \(version 1\)](#) in July 2024, which outlined potential conference goals, leadership, and business models.

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The paper was refined through feedback gathered during three online meetings, involving participants from a range of existing events as well as invited organisations. This led to [version 2](#), which was shared for broader discussion in November 2024.

ReSA led a consultation process involving a [survey](#), webinars, and direct feedback to gather input and identify stakeholders interested in shepherding the development of an event. The [final report](#), released in early 2025, outlines two potential approaches for creating three event options in 2026: 1) a sequential approach to creating three events, beginning with workshops at existing events in 2025, to build momentum towards all three options taking place in 2026, or 2) form committees led by ReSA to begin development of all three options in early 2025, to enable their convening in 2026. ReSA has begun forming [committees](#) to move forward with planning these events.

International Council of RSE Associations

In 2024, ReSA was delighted to become the secretariat for the International Council of RSE Associations. The Council provides a formal platform for established national and multinational RSE associations to collaborate on RSE-related issues. Currently, the Council includes nine national and two multinational/regional associations. Delegates from the established RSE associations meet regularly to coordinate, discuss, and collaborate around research software engineering/engineers. It is predicted that by 2030, at least 50 countries globally will have RSE associations. In addition to working with leaders in the RSE community through the Council, ReSA supports individual RSEs and RSE research through its resources, such as Resources on how to create a research software engineering (RSE) group (within an organisation) or association (national, etc); RSE Worldwide: Opportunities to Strengthen the Global RSE Community; and Directions for Research Software Engineering Research.

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Task Forces

ReSA welcomed two new task forces in 2024: Actionable Guidelines for FAIR Research Software and FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Review.

Actionable FAIR4RS

The goal of this task force is to create actionable, step-by-step guidelines for researchers to make their research software Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). While the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Principles offer a general framework, there are currently no specific instructions for researchers to follow. The task force aims to break down these principles, tailor them to different research contexts, and develop practical guidelines. The group will build on existing work, seek community feedback, and eventually publish the guidelines.

FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Review

The FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles), developed by ReSA, the Research Data Alliance (RDA), and FORCE11, were published in March 2022 after extensive community input. These principles aim to enhance the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) of research software, promoting transparency, reproducibility, and reusability. While there has been notable adoption, challenges remain in fully implementing the principles. The ReSA task force, in collaboration with the RDA Software Source Code Interest Group, seeks to identify areas where the principles have and have not been adopted and understand the reasons behind these gaps.

Other ReSA task forces

Ongoing ReSA task forces, including *Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS)*, *Code Availability*, and *Research Software Authorship and Contribution* continued their activities.

The PRO4RS Working Group, co-convened by ReSA and RDA, published *Resources for supporting policy change in research institutions in practice: A report from Subgroup 2*. This output highlights the challenges that the working group is addressing and its motivation for looking at them. It then summarises a variety of existing resources relevant to different stakeholders. As software becomes an essential element of research across all domains, there is a growing need for research organisations to recognise its importance and provide policies and guidance to support the sustainability and impact of research software in modern research processes and outputs.

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Collaborations

Research software is critical to the future of AI-driven research

ReSA, in collaboration with the [Digital Research Alliance of Canada](#)—one of ReSA's [Founding Members](#)—co-authored a [position paper](#) emphasising the critical role of research software in artificial intelligence (AI)-driven research. The paper outlines recommendations for stakeholders on how to incorporate research software into their AI initiatives. It covers both generative AI, currently being explored as a tool for new research, and traditional machine learning, which has already had a significant impact across disciplines. The paper highlights the often overlooked dependency of AI on software—such as for data preparation, model training, and implementation—and stresses the need for recognising software and its developers as vital components of AI infrastructure. It also explores how some countries are aligning AI strategies with investments in research software and provides actionable recommendations across three key areas from the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#): research software practice, ecosystem, and personnel.

The FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Principles after two years: an adoption update

ReSA led the drafting of an update on the adoption of the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Principles. The [report](#) assesses the state of the FAIR4RS principles two years after their release in 2022, highlighting progress across five key areas of cultural change: policies, incentives, communities, training, and infrastructure. These areas collectively aim to enhance the FAIRness of research software. While

substantial progress has been made, challenges persist in fully adopting the principles. Notable initiatives include the development of national guidelines for software management plans and the creation of resources to help institutions implement FAIR practices. The report emphasises the ongoing need for continued efforts to simplify and integrate the FAIR4RS principles in their entirety. See also this [ReSA blog post](#).

Enabling open science through research code

[Enabling Open Science through Research Code](#) was a six-part series co-organised by ReSA's community engagement partners in Africa and Asia—[Talarify](#) and the [RSE Asia Association](#)—along with [RSSE Africa](#), the [African Reproducibility Network](#), and ReSA. The series aimed to provide researchers who write code with opportunities to learn best practices, expand their networks, and showcase their work, covering essential topics such as reproducibility, research code documentation, and testing. Past episodes are available for viewing. We congratulate our partners for successfully engaging a global community of research software engineers (RSEs), helping them enhance their skills and contribute to the growth of the research software community.

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ReSA's partnership with CZI's Essential Open Source Software for Science (EOSS) program

ReSA was proud to collaborate with the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) as a non-funding partner for EOSS Cycle 6, leveraging its expertise in research software funding and helping expand the program's global reach. EOSS Cycle 6 marked CZI's first multi-funder initiative, funded in partnership with Wellcome Trust and the Kavli Foundation; and designed in partnership with ReSA.

In July, the CZI Open Science Team released a report detailing the impact of the EOSS program. With 193 grants and \$51.8 million in funding to date, EOSS represents the largest initiative addressing the needs of scientific software for research.

Image by Chan Zuckerberg Initiative

Join ReSA

Get involved and make an impact by:

- Joining task forces focused on specific activities
- Staying informed with our regular, insightful newsletter
- Become an Organisational Member, support a task force, or make a donation
- Raising awareness of the critical role of software in research by sharing ReSA resources
- Signing or supporting the Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability (ADORE.software)
- Connecting with fellow community members on LinkedIn, Bluesky, and Mastodon, or at our events
- Joining the ReSA Slack to collaborate with decision-makers and key influencers on the latest community developments
- Providing information about new funding calls to the Research Software Funding Opportunities database
- Contributing resources and guidelines; ideas for task forces, events, and news; or if you have other ideas for ReSA, then let us know.

We look forward to welcoming you!

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our community, Founding Members, and Organisational Members – without whom none of this work would have been possible. This project has been made possible in part by Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, grant number 2024-22426, *Research Software Alliance: Catalyzing community-led collaborations*. ReSA is a fiscally sponsored project of Code for Science & Society and governed by the ReSA Steering Committee.

ReSA is supported by the community through Organisational and Founding Members, project grants, task force support, and donations. An overview of ReSA income and expenditures is available online. In 2024, ReSA received resourcing of USD \$378,295 (\$318,295 cash and \$60,000 in-kind). Our grants are also available on Open Grants.

Consider supporting ReSA:
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